

Nepal-India Relations: Efforts to Review 1950's Treaty (Special Acts of EPG)

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Abstract:- This paper attempts to highlight bilateral relation between Nepal and India with special reference to the efforts made by Nepal for reviewing or repealing 1950's peace and friendship treaty. The paper highly focused on the impact of 1950's treaty of peace and amity held between weakened Rana rulers and newly freed India. Further, the paper has stressed on the efforts of Eminent Persons Group, EPG on reviewing the treaties held between the two old friends of south Asia who shares long socio-cultural similarity as well as open border. Actually, Nepal has been victimized due to unequal and dominating treaty i.e. often compared with Versailles treaty, and Prime Minister Man Mohan Adhikari had raised voice against this treaty for the first time even being in post that started open discourse about this treaty and it came up to the course of formation of EPG too with the motive of studying unequal treaties hold between Nepal and India.

Keywords: - Indo-Nepal, Treaty, dominating, Eminent, peace and Amity, isolation, appeasement.

I. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- To analyze bilateral relation between Nepal and India
- To find out the efforts made by Nepal to review 1950's treaty with especial reference to role of EPG.

II. METHODOLOGY OF STUDY:

The methodology undertaken in this research work includes descriptive and analytical methods. The past events occurred and made, (bilaterally and multilateral) by two nations are entertained here. Likewise, primary and secondary sources that are available on this subject have been used. Primary sources that are: policies, reports, official documents and interview of the policy makers are used. In secondary sources, the major works of different prominent authors in the field have also been included and analyzed in neutral and intellectual ways.

III. INTRODUCTION:

Since the beginning of 1950's, Nepal-India relation under peace and amity Treaty began. Politically, Nepal-India relations have faced many fluctuations. Before unification, Nepal was not taken as a separate political entity after unification till 1845 Nepal had followed foreign policy laid by Prithivi Narayan Shah during the Rana regime, Nepal followed a policy of isolation and appeasement from rest of the world and British India, respectively. In 1923 the treaty signed with Nepal by British under which Nepal was recognized as a sovereign

state, but in matters of foreign affairs and defense Nepal hardly had any independence but provisions of 1950's treaty made Nepal once under India's security realm as well as it became like a nail inside shoes worn as. That's why, the question of reviewing or repealing of this treaty has always been the hot issue and got high priority since the time of Prime Minister K.P. Oli in 2016. It's a result of Oli's firm determination of sovereign equality of Nepal and India, he gave high priority to EPG and EPG worked seriously on this matter.

IV. DISCUSSION

India's political movements, ideologies and major incidences have always influenced Nepal from Indian undue influences but it was impossible because history shows that national movement of 1857 and congress movement of 1885 effected Nepal a lot and some leaders of Nepal also took part in it. In 1947, when British left India and the ruling power came in hands of congress leadership that made Rana rulers of Nepal orphans like. Reason for this tension was not only power change in India; but because of changes taking place in Nepal and Demand for changing and improvement in leadership by Nepalese political parties and people.

Political aspects, open border one, of India towards Nepal was influenced by its own political ideology, experiences and expectations but hidden aspect is to drive Nepali politics in the way they liked. Since beginning, India wanted stable and democratic government. India puts always vested interest and makes it fulfill through the weak governments like Ranas during 1950, Panchayat during 1989/90, and King Gyanendra's autocracy rule in 2005.

During 1950's beginning demand for political reforms was going strong in Nepal and that was the reason, the rulers of Nepal agreed to do some changes. India also supported reforms and wanted reforms to take place as per the rulers of democracy; but India never wanted to change the whole system in one go. Pandit Nehru had said if everything will change on one go, then it will only increase problem for Nepal (*shaha, 1968*). This vision have two dimensions i.e. Nepal could achieve the goal of democracy with gradual reforms and another is Nepal can be under India's control for a long time or dependency of Nepal in India would remain for a long political journey. For the second interest, India made Peace and Amity Treaty with Ranas and threw Ranas from the power in 1950. But up to the last break Mohan Shamsher tried to get Indian favor to retain in power. As the efforts to appease India Mohan Shamsher visited Indian capital for talks Nehru told in the parliament it is not possible for the Indian Government to

tolerate any invasion of Nepal from anywhere even though there was no military alliance between the two countries. Any possible invasion of Nepal would inevitably involve in the safety of India. (Upadhya, 2018, p67))

Mohan Shamsher, however sought to win Indian support for his regime by projecting the Rana System as a bulwark against communist subversion from the North. After the follow up talks, New Delhi and Kathmandu formalized their new relationship on July 31, 1950 by signing treaties of Peace and Friendship as well as trade and commerce (Rose, 71 p, 186).

❖ Scenario of Treaty

The bilateral treaty held between Nepal India in 1950 was directed towards the establishment of desired and its favored relationship. This treaty was done with the weakening Ranas who were seeking Indian support to retain in power but unfortunately after the three months of the treaty held Ranarchy was wiped-out. *THE TREATY WAS OFTENLY COMPAIRED WITH VERSAILES TREATY* because the signatories of the treaty were also not of equal status, one was CPN SINGH the Indian ambassador to Nepal and from Nepal side it was prime minister Mohan Shumser. The unilateral, dominating and provision with humiliating Nepali sovereign independency has dragged civilian towards anti- Indian activities. Mostly, article ii, iv, v, vi and vii are condemnable.

Being careful with changed political scenario, Nepal and India both have been agreed to review, adjust and update the treaty. Late Prime Minister Sushil Koirala and his counterpart Mr. Modi had been agreed to review the treaty in 2014. The leftist parties of Nepal are being benefited through the anti Indian sentiment created by Indian elderly brother behavior. Nepal's quest of independence and sovereignty under the treaty is the major concern of Nepali people. Nepalese independent foreign policy and self-reliant defense policy is our major concern. (<https://www.tandfonline.com>).

❖ Why does Nepal want review?

A. Positive Angle

Articles 6 and 7 of the treaty reads, the two countries agree to grant, on reciprocal basis, to citizens of one country in territories of other, same privileges in matters of residence, ownership of property, participation in trade and commerce, movement and other privileges of similar nature. This enables the Nepali and Indian nationals to move freely across the border without passport or visa, live and work in either country and own property or do trade or business in either country. There is a significant number of Nepalese living, owning property and working or doing business in India as beneficial aspect of treaty for Nepal. Similarly many Indians live, own property and do business in Nepal.

B. Nepalese Reading

The positive aspect of the treaty is that it has recognized Nepalese sovereignty and the latest discourse on 1950's Nepal-India Peace and friendship treaty begun and it was the first time that India and Nepal formally discussed the treaty article-wise. Nepal's demand to review Article 2, 5, 6 and 7 of the treaty highly appreciating because the provisions of the treaty has undermined Nepal's sovereignty and put it at a distinct disadvantage in terms of trade economic development and movement of people of two nations. Nepal's reservation to the provisions of the treaty gives India an upper hand to dictate Nepalese foreign and security affairs.

- **Article II** of the treaty states that, "the two governments hereby undertake to inform each other of any serious friction or misunderstanding with any neighboring state likely to cause any breach in the friendly relations subsisting between the two governments. Prime facie, the provision seems good to both but the hidden interest of India to check Chinese interest in Nepal. And it is India that violated this Article. India fought wars with China in 1962 but it never informed Nepal about the armed conflicts in advance. Thus, the notion of mutual Security commitment automatically came to an end. As per the treaty, when one side violates the Treaty, it losses relevance.
- **Article III** reads, the general provision regarding diplomatic privileges and immunities as customarily granted by international law but the Indian ambassador violets this privileges too. As Ex Indian Ambassador to Nepal, Ranjeet Rae visited in Manang, Mustang and other areas of Himalayan region controversially.
- **ARTICLE IV:** the two governments agree to appoint consuls General. Consuls, vice-consuls and other places in each others' territory as may be agreed too. But these provisions also have been violated by India the consulate office established in Nepal's Biratnagar. Actually, it was a temporary office which had been set up during floods in Nepal and north Bihar and continues to function since then but it did not back after the completion of the task P.M. Oli (when?) spoke strongly about this issue and this consul's office was removed.
- **ARTICLE V:** of the treaty states that, "the Government of Nepal shall be free to import from or through the territory of India, arms, ammunitions or war like materials and equipment necessary for the security of Nepal. The procedure for giving effect to this arrangement shall be worked out by the two governments acting in consultation." It is controversial, ambiguous and unequal. The Indian side has been interpreting that Nepal should consult it if the former imports weapons and military materials from other countries. India had imposed economic blockade on Nepal in 1988, occurring Nepal for purchasing weapons and ammunitions from China. Actually, Nepal bought weapons and ammunitions from China because Indian arms were five times more expensive than that of

Chinese. In fact this provision challenges Nepalese independency that's why this treaty should be revised or replaced.

- **ARTICLE VI:** states that, “each Governments undertakes, in token of the neighborly friendship between India and Nepal, to give to the nationals of the other, in its territory, national treatment with regard to participation in industrial and economic development of such territory and to the grant of concessions and contracts, relating to such development.

This article runs counter to the country's existing law that bars the foreigners from buying and selling properly in Nepal. Theoretically, it goes against the fair rules of global trade that demands that all companies be given equal treatment. Practically viewing, Nepal is unable to benefit from this article. Its economy and private sector can hardly compete with that of India. The matter of facts is that Indian companies dominate Nepal's trade, market and industries. But, here is a pertinent question: how many Nepalese companies have no concessions and contracts in India in the last 66 years? Perhaps, there is no positive answer to this question.

- **ARTICLE VII:** is even more dangerous. It further reads, “The governments of India and Nepal agree to grant on a reciprocal basis, to the nationals of one country in the territories of the other the same privileges in the matter of residence, ownership of property, participation in trade and commerce, movement and other privilege of a similar nature. Source (The letter of Exchange). (Source: Upreti, 2013)

The letter of exchange of the Treaty insists that Nepal should give priority to Indian Government or its citizens to harness the natural resources and open industrial estate here. There is demographic and topographic dichotomy between Nepal and India, so this provision clearly disfavors the country's socio-economy. Many viewed that India wants to capture Nepal's natural resources by invoking this Article. It was first used in the construction of Kohalpur-Banabasa road. A Chinese company was awarded to build the road with financial support of the World Bank, Saudi Fund and OPEC Fund. But, Nepal could not resist India's pressure and it was finally given to the latter that could not complete it even in 15 years. It was supposed to be finished in five years. The Sindhuli-Bardiwas road is also made narrow due to India's protest otherwise it was proposed to make 4 lanes.

Further, Nepalese scholars argue that the Treaty was signed with a Rana Prime Minister who was not elected by the people and therefore does not represent the Nepali political consensus. They also refer to the unequal status of the signatories. Likewise, the treaty is concluded as a legacy of British imperialism. After 1947, the relations between India and Nepal had to start on a new scale of heightened ideological passions of democracy. Even though the two countries were ready to write their opinion during the British rule were not done away with. The standstill

Agreement signed in 1949 accepted all the previous treaties signed as valid till new treaties and agreements could be signed.

In fact, the treaty of Peace and Amity of 1950 was a reflection of the treaty of Peace and Friendship signed in 1923 but with changes made to suit the political context of the time. Six and half decades have gone by the reference to the general perception on Nepal-India relations and continue to haunt the Nepalese elites. It has become a yard stick to critically measure the policies with India even though Nepal had good working relations with the British. CPN (UML), CPN Maoists, CPN (ML), Janamorcha Nepal, Nepal-workers and Peasants Party (NWPP) and other Communist parties have often declared India's relation with Nepal as imperialistic, hegemonistic and responsible for signing unequal treaties with Nepal. Indian annexation of Sikkim (1975) reflected Indian intervention policy towards shall nations.

It is also argued that this treaty of Peace and Friendship is an outmoded treaty and derogations from it are common place. Since both countries have led many of its provisions fall into disuse in the last 50 years, the time has come to review the treaty and replace it by a new one. Nepal has a fear psychology that as India had forced Nepalese to leave from North-eastern states i.e. Assam and Meghalaya in the late 1980's. That's why; Nepal argues that India should not expect Nepal to conform to a treaty to which India itself is unable to conform.

Another argument of Nepal is about the influx of Indian Labors into Nepal. The small country cannot bear the Indians flow in Nepal. Likewise, this treaty is described not only unequal but as an attack on Nepal's sovereignty on the ground that the circumstances in which the treaty was signed have changed and therefore, there is no relevance of this treaty anymore.

The next but vital criticism of this treaty is surrounded around the politico-strategic aspects of the same. It is alleged that India has been more concerned about its strategic and security interests in the Himalayas and has ignored Nepal's sovereignty (article 5). Likewise, Nepal has reservations on clause 6 that allows the citizens to participate in the industrial and national development in each other's country and clause 7, which grants the citizen the right to reside, own property, participate in trade and commerce and enjoy other privileges in one another's country. The demand of India of reciprocal 'National treatment' for its citizens in Nepalese territory and access to all the Nepal's Natural resources, while Nepalese citizens are being discriminated against while acquiring property in India is inconsistent with India's exercise of full sovereignty over the years, there have been many instances when India has ignored the provisions of the treaty. If we see article 2, it also shows serious condition targeting to check Chinese security or possible entrance in Nepal.

C. Indian Eyes

But the Indian eyes on the provisions of the treaty are opposite to Nepal. India still wants to continue this treaty standstill. But due to high pressure of Nepal and Nepali people, India become ready to have negotiations bilaterally and EPG was formed (*Dr Bhes Bahadur Thapa , Nilambar Acharya, Surya Nath Upadhyaya Rajan Bhattarai FROM NEPALI SIDE AND Bhagat singh koshiyari , B C Upreti M P Lama and Jayanta Prasad from Indian side*) whereas prime minister ManMohanari ,the president of then CPN(UML) ,had formally raised the voice for the timely revision of the treaty. Together, the revolting Maoist also gave stress on the need of the amendment of the treaty before starting the insurgency.they had presented forty points demand giving first priority to this issue.While the demand for the revision, repeal or amendment of the treaty has been taken by Indian as the growing tie between Nepal and China. In fact, the relation between Nepal China during the first and present Oli,s primer time is rapidly increasing which has been taken psychological threat to India. But the Madhesi parties believe that border management as an inevitable corollary to revision with devastate the special relation between the people of Terai of Nepal and Bihars as well as Uttar Pradesh of India. The traditional ties of Roti-Beti in the region cannot be ignored by those proposing revision.

India has expressed its readiness to 'review' the treaty, the discourse on revision of 1950,s treaty in the decade resulted EPG and it worked seriously through its two years tenure with nine bilateral meetings.

Eminent Persons Group (EPG) Meetings:-

The notion of revision of the treaty got speedy pace during the time of K P Oli ,s priministership and both the Government- appointed Eminent Persons Group (EPG) with the mandate (following the meeting between Prime Minister K.P. Sharma Oli and Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 20 February 2016 included taking a serious look at a possible review of the friendship treaty which was concluded decades ago) to make rigorous discussions . Dr. Bhes Bahadur Thapa, coordinator of Nepali team to the EPG urged for betterment border policing and effective regulation of movement of people ,the border between the two sides is already delineated and the border posts are already in place but many of these marks are damaged indicating poor maintenance There is an urgent need to police the border better to stop cross-border crime and ensure regulated movement of people," Mr. Thapa said, explaining that the India-Nepal border needs to be upgraded with new security measures. *The EPG was constituted during the India visit of Mr. K.P. Sharma Oli on February 20, 2016 towards the end of the blockade that was imposed by the Madhesi agitators from Nepal's southern border. As per the agreement, the EPG is to consist of eight members with four members representing each side.*

The 1st meeting of the EPG had taken place in Kathmandu in July, 2016. As per the mandate, the two sides will have to prepare and submit a joint document to

their respective governments at the end of their two years tenure and will hold meetings in each three months.

Kathmandu, July 4: The first meeting of the EPG has kicked off in the capital. Deputy Prime Minister Kamal Thapa expressed confidence that the meeting will contribute to strengthen the historically existing bilateral relations. He further added that Nepal had entered to the journey of prosperity after issuing a democratic constitution, adding that the bilateral ties should be strengthened for the development and prosperity of the both countries. Similarly, coordinator of the EPG from India Bharat Singh Koshiyari, Chief Minister of Uttaranchal Pradesh, India, said that they will review bilateral ties and will help strengthen it in the days ahead.

Koshiyari viewed that Nepal is India's good neighbor. Likewise, coordinator at the Nepali EPG Dr. Bhekhd Bd. Thapa, former Minister for foreign affairs, said that the meeting will help to reach the bilateral relations to a new height, adding that they will Jointly study the past bilateral treaties and agreements. The 1st meeting is said to be centered on preparing the procedure and modality of the meeting.

The second EPG meeting held on October, 2016 in New Delhi. The first meeting held in Kathmandu in July was a preparatory session. It identified five areas *political issues, government to government relations, cultural issues, trade and connectivity* for discussion and preparing recommendations. The top agenda of the EPG is reviewing the 1950 Treaty and other treaties related to trade and transit. The Indian side has asked Nepal to come up with a clear position on how to amend the 'unequal' treaty. The Nepali side, according to a member, maintains that there should be discussion on it instead of one side presenting its position.

The key clauses of the treaty that Nepal wants to amend are the need for India's consent for Nepal to purchase defense hardware, recruitment of Gorkha soldiers and preference for India in the development of Nepal's natural resources." The Group member Rajan Bhattarai said, "Many provisions of the treaty are *no* redundant. Many international and regional treaties signed after 1950 should be taken into consideration." (<https://www.ekantipur.com>). He further said, "This is not only reviewing the past agreements, treaties and understandings, we will also suggest a new framework of relationship that should be adopted between the two countries in the 21st century." The Indian side has realized that the treaty should be amended. The Indian team has expressed its readiness to consider any proposal that Nepal tables at the meeting.

The third meeting of EPG began on April 5th, 2017 to make further discussions on the course of revision of Nepal India peace and friendship treaty, 1950.The two days EPG meeting was highly concentrated on update and revision according to the changed time and situation Mr .Bhes Bahadur Thapa, the FPG coordinator of Nepali side,

viewed so. To define and drive Nepal India relations in changed political scenario, the meeting had focused on review of various aspects of bilateral relationship between the two countries.

Nepal has proposed to review and contextualize the Nepal-India Peace and Friendship Treaty which can be the bedrock on modern relations between the two south Asian nations i. e. Nepal and India, the meeting is focused on reviewing or revisiting the treaties, agreements and arrangements between the two countries making out a roadmap of the bilateral ties that is characterized by social, economic, religious and cultural aspects, of bilateral issues (www.xinhuanet.com).

The 4th EPG meeting held on 29 to 31st May, 2017 at Deharadun. In this meeting India agreed to discuss further on various issues including the controversial 1950 peace and friendship Treaty, trade and transit between the two countries and the utilization of water resources. Both sides were positive to study and review all treaties between the two countries within two years. This meeting decided to visit bordering areas to understand the views of the local people. Holding talks to forge broad consensus on contentious issues between the two countries and also in the cards (<https://myrepublicnagariknetwork.com>).

According to members, peace and friendship treaty 1950 continues to take the central stage of deliberations since its first meeting. Discussions were made on key provisions of the Treaty after Nepali team presented clause-wise viewpoint on how it wants to amend the 65 years old treaty. The achievement so far is that serious deliberations have begun on some key provisions of the treaty and discussions are advancing gradually. Many provisions of the treaty remain unimplemented, some of them are redundant, while others need modifications in the changed context of several international treaties and conventions to which both Nepal and India are parties.

While the Indian side has already expressed its reactions to some issues, it is yet to come up with a clear viewpoint on some others, especially the sensitive ones. As Nepal had said during the previous engagements that the treaty was unequal and redundant, the Indian side had requested to come up with the terms on how it wants to replace/amend the treaty. This meeting highly focused on day to day problems faced by Nepal and long term issues related to transit and trade between the two countries. The meeting decided to enter border issue in next round talks.

On 7th Oct, 2017, the fifth meeting of the EPG had held on. At the meeting, Surya Prasad Upadhyay presented a working paper on Nepal-India co-operation and utility on water resources. As agreed in 4th EPG meeting, Nepal proposed removing illegal structures built on no-man's land along the Nepal-India border. Nepal focused on maintaining international standard and ensures scientific management of the border between the two countries. No-man's land has encroached from the Indian side Nepali side

has found to have encroached the 'no-man-land' in some places (<https://www.spotlightnepal.com>).

One of the Nepal side EPG members Dr. Rajan Bhattarai said that Nepal has proposed removing illegal structures along the border in line with the existing international standards. While Nepal-India shares border dispute in different places, the illegal structures built on the no-man's land have also caused the dispute between the two countries. The head of the EPG from Nepal, Bhekh Bahadur Thapa said that they have proposed making the border further secure. He further viewed that Nepal-India border needs to be regulated, not closed, to stop illegal activities along the bordering areas. He further opined:

"We need to understand the definition of an open border of the past in the changed context. Both sides have stepped back from the traditional concept of 'openness'"

The Nepali side had put forth all issues of contention including 1950 Peace and Friendship Treaty with Indians side during the two day EPG meeting held in Kathmandu. Mr. Bhekh Bd. Thapa said that they have yet to reach agreement on whether to replace or amend the 1950 treaty with India or not. We are convinced that this will remain in the status quo. We would not wait for 70 years if this was to be scrapped altogether. This is the reason why we have chosen the path of the improvement.

The Nepali side presented its position on how it works to review of Article 2, 5, 6 and 7 of the Treaty. This time side put forth its views clearly after some e.g members from the Indian side complained that their counterparts were failing to come up with "clear position" on how they went to amend the treaty (<https://borneobulletin.com.bn>). Thus 5th EPG meeting concludes here in Kathmandu without any tangible results (www.reviewnepal.com).

On January 11, 2018 sixth EPG meeting held, this meeting got significance because the Nepali EPG team hold separate discussions with the top leaders of the three major political parties including Sher Bahadur Deuba (NC), Khadga Prasad Oli (CPN, UML) and Puspa Kumar Dahal (CPN-MC). In the meeting, Deuba has reportedly inquired about India's stand on various issues pertaining to Indo-Nepal ties.

According to Rajan Bhattarai an EPG member from Nepal, both the sides have held discussions on various challenging issues between the two countries covering the 1950 Nepal-India Peace and Friendship Treaty, utilization of hydro resources, border management and issues related to Trade and Transit (<https://www.nepalisansar.com>).

7th EPG meeting held on 25th February, 2018 in Kathmandu. On this meeting various bilateral issues including 1950 Peace and Friendship Treaty, Trade environment, border and hydropower were discussed during two-day's meeting. Dr. Bhekh Bahadur Thapa and EPG coordinator of Indian side Bhagat Singh Koshiyari said that a report is being prepared to take bilateral relations

to a new height. Dr. Thapa said that issues from 1950 treaty to current border-related concerns were addressed and a positive report on it would be submitted within few months (ddnews.gov.in>national Kathmandu-7).

Indian coordinator Bhagat Singh Koshiyari expressed confidence that no side will be disappointed with the report. EPG is a Joint mechanism consisting experts and intellectuals from India and Nepal.

The eight meeting of the EPG on Nepal-India Relations, which had kicked off in New Delhi on 12th April, 2018. The meeting, which was focused on finalizing the report to be presented to both the governments, made further progress on bilateral issues under discussion and the next meeting has been fixed for June 1st to 3rd in Kathmandu, according to Rajan Bhattarai, an EPG member representing Nepal, “we were able to narrow down the perspectives in this meeting and will try to make the next meeting the last one to finalize the report.”

At the end of the 7th meeting in Kathmandu, the EPG members had said that they were giving final touches to the report to be presented to both the governments. During the recent visit of Prime Minister K.P. Oli in India, Oli and his Indian counterpart Narendra Modi had also said that recommendations put forth by the EPG would be accepted. PM Oli’s India visit has definitely given fresh inputs in this regard (<https://thehimalayantimes.com>).

EPG, the ninth and final meeting, concluded on 29th June, 2018 in Kathmandu, Capital city of Nepal. During the meeting, representatives from Nepal and India deliberated up on various bilateral issues including 1950 Peace and Friendship Treaty, trade, transit and border. During the last meeting, EPG successfully prepared joint report which will be submitted to PMs of both the countries. It has agreed to update all the bilateral treaties and agreements reached in past between Nepal and India in line with the present global political reality (<https://currentaffairs.gktoday.in>).

V. CONCLUSION

To settle down bilateral issues between Nepal and India deeply rooted since 1950, the EPG was formed in January 2016 by Governments of Nepal and India, with ToR of reviewing the entire controversial provisions of Nepal-India relations and update bilateral agreements and treaties. The joint mechanism consisting experts and intellectuals from Nepal and India including four-four members from India and Nepal did its best efforts to make acceptable report.

The mandated to review various aspects of the bilateral relations including Nepal- India Friendship Treaty, 1950 and provide suggestions on ways to reshape bilateral relation held between the two countries. During earlier meeting of EPG, Nepali side had presented facts and figures regarding need to review Nepal-India Peace and Friendship Treaty of 1950 so as to update is as required by time and situation.

The treaty is a bilateral issue between Nepal and India aimed at establishing close strategic relationship between two very close south Asian neighbors. It was held on July 31, 1950 at Kathmandu by the PM of Nepal Mohan Shamsher Jung B. Rana and then Indian ambassador to Nepal Chandreshwor Prasad Narayan Singh. The treaty has 10 articles that permit free movement of people and goods between two countries and close relationship and collaboration on matters of defense and foreign affairs. It envisages for eternal Peace and Friendship between two nations and recognizes and respect complete sovereignty, territorial integrity and independence of each other. The report of EPG is ready to be handled to P.M. Modi and Oli but Indian south bloc is not ready to accept the report that may be because of general election in India or other reasons. If India want to improve relations with Nepal it should accept EPG report and implement it otherwise the Treaty Indian sentiment won't decrease among Nepali. P M Oli views EPG report will be accepted by both and implemented soon.

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